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AWARENESS AND APPRAISAL OF UTILISATION OF INSECTICIDE
TREATED NETS AMONG INHABITANTS OF WARRI METROPOLIS

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Abstract

Malaria is a parasitic disease which is easily preventable, treatable and curable, but still remains one of the major public health problems in Nigeria. Insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) have long been used against mosquito bites, and have been shown to give substantial protection against malaria. This study was designed to appraise the awareness and usage of insecticide treated nets among inhabitants of Warri metropolis. Six hundred inhabitants of Warri metropolis were selected using convenience sampling technique. A self-structured questionnaire validated and with a reliability of 0.72 was used for data collection.

Percentages, frequency counts were used to analyse data collected. Findings showed that 71.5% (429) inhabitants of Warri metropolis did not use insecticide treated nets daily and 52% (312) were aware of the advantages of using ITNs to prevent malaria parasite. It was recommended that there is need for all stakeholders in health education to increase public campaign on the use of ITNs.

Introduction

In Nigeria malaria is endemic throughout the country. World Health Organization (WHO) estimated malaria mortality rate for children under five in Nigeria at 729 per 100,000. Malaria has a great morbidity and mortality rate than any other infectious disease in the world (World Malarial Report, 2005); a child will be sick of malaria between two and four times in one year (FMOH 2005). Malaria is one of the leading causes of child deaths in Africa. It is transmitted from person to person by infected mosquitoes. It involves flu-like symptoms including fever. There is evidence connecting malaria with death (particularly in children under 5), anemia, splenomegaly (enlarged spleen), other nutrition-deficiency-related indicators, and low birth weight. It is also believed that malaria can cause permanent disability (hearing impairment, visual impairment, epilepsy, etc.). The malaria burden as reported in the country is on the increase in spite of numerous interventions that have been instituted. The obstacles to the success of these interventions are socio-cultural, economic and political in nature. According to UNICEF (2004) it kills a child somewhere in the world every 30 seconds. 90% of deaths occur in Africa, where malaria accounts for about one in five of all childhood deaths. Each year, there are approximately 5.15 million people the majority of whom are young children in sub-Saharan Africa (Snow, 2005).

The use of insecticide-treated nets (ITN) helps in preventing mosquitoes bite which will help in reducing malaria parasite. ITNs is a net (usually a bed net) . designed to block mosquitoes physically, that has been treated with safe, residual insecticide for the purpose of killing and repelling mosquitoes, which carry malaria. However, it has its own limitations, A long-lasting insecticide-treated net (LLIN) is an ITN designed to remain effective for multiple years without retreatment. The World Health Organization recommends that LLINs be distributed for free to achieve universal coverage (one LLIN for every 1.8 people in the target population) of those at risk for malaria. An I-LIN distribution involves surveying people to determine the need for LLINs; delivering LLINs; and promoting the use of LLINs. It appears that there has been a shift in emphasis over the last several years from targeted coverage (aiming primarily to cover children under five and pregnant women with ITNs) to universal coverage (aiming to protect everyone in a community with ITNs). LLINs are assumed to last two to three years on average. Insecticide. treated nets (ITNs) have long been used against mosquito bites, and have been shown to give substantial protection against malaria. This does not apply to Longlasting Insecticide Treated Nets (LLINs).

LLINs are manufactured in a different way. Two brands have been approved by the WHO Pesticide Evaluation Scheme (WHOPES), and can be recommended for use. One brand is composed of permethrin inside a polyethylene thread. The other comprises deltamethrin stuck onto polyester fibre, however, experience with this net is limited, and only monitoring over time will show whether it lives up to its promise. LLINs last, in general, for four to five years, and are washresistant up to 20 washes without the need for insecticide retreatment, The LLINs made of polyethylene are stronger and more durable, and may be the most appropriate option for complex emergencies. It is certainly clear that, in LLINs, the insecticide is present and effective for much longer than in ITNs. Whatever type Of net is being considered, quality control will always be important.

Research Questions

- 1 . Would there be awareness of insecticide treated nets among inhabitants Of Warri metropolis?
2. Would there be effective usage of insecticide treated nets among inhabitantS of Warri metropolis?
3. What are the challenges to the effective usage of insecticide treated nets among inhabitants of Warri metropolis?
- 4, What has been the connection between LLIN usage and drops in malaria morbidity among inhabitants of Warri metropolis?

Methodology

Six hundred inhabitants of warri metropolis were selected using convenient sampling techniques. A self-structured questionnaire validated and subjected to a reliability test and with a value of 0.72 was used for data collection. Percentages, frequency counts were used to analyse data collected.

Result

The data collected were analysed, and interpreted as follows:

Table 1: Awareness of insecticide treated nets and long lasting insecticide treated nets

		343	68	189	600
2	Insecticide treatment nets get easily damaged and Diltv	(60.7%) 364	(15.3%) 92	(24%) 144	10 (100%)
3	ITNs are efficient in preventing mosquito from biting humans.	(52%) 312	(42%) 288	-	(100%) 600
4	Insecticide treated nets give much more protection than untreated ones.	(20%) 121	(12.8%) 77	(67%) 402	(100%) 600
5	I prefer other methods like sprays, and window nets against mosquitoes bite to ITNs	(85.5%) 513	(14.5%) 87	-	(100%) 600
6	It IS certainly clear that LLINs is ITNs.	(30.7%) 181	(4.796%) 28	(65.2%) 391	(100%) 600
7	I-LIN means Long Lasting Insecticide Treated Nets.	(20.5%) 123	(37.3%) 224	(42.3%) 254	(100%) 601
8	know LLITNs is better than ITNs.	(16.17%) 97	(50.7%) 304	(33.2%) 199	(100%) 600

SN	Awareness of ITNS/LLINs	Agreed	Disagreed	Undecided	Total
1	ITNs means Insecticide Treatment Nets.	(57.7%)	(11.3%)	(31.5%)	(100%)

Table I revealed that 343(57.2%) respondents agreed that ITNs means insecticide treated nets, 11.3%) disagreed, and 189(31.5%) were undecided. The percentage

rating shows that Agreed is ranked highest, followed by Undecided and Disagreed. This shows that majority of the respondents have the knowledge of ITNS. 364(60.7%) respondents agreed that ITNs have been used against mosquito bites and have given substantial protection against malaria: 92(15.3%) disagreed and 144(24%) were Undecided. The percentage rating shows that Agreed is ranked highest. Also 312(52%) respondents agreed that ITN is very efficient in preventing mosquito from biting humans while 288(42%) disagreed. The percentage rating shows that agreed is ranked highest followed by disagreed. 402(67%) agreed that ITNs give much more protection than untreated ones, 121 (20.2%), disagreed and 77(12.8%) were undecided. The percentage rating shows that agreed ranked highest. 5 respondents agreed that they prefer other methods like insecticide spray and window nets against mosquitoes bites to ITN, 87(14.5%) disagreed. 181(30.7%) respondents agreed that LLIN is ITNs, 28(4.7%) disagreed and 391 (65.2%) were Undecided. The percentage rating shows that undecided is ranked highest. Moreover, .5% respondents agreed that LLITNs means long lasting insecticide treated nets: 224(37.3%) disagreed and 254(42.3%) were Undecided. The percentage rating shows that Undecided total is ranked highest, followed by Disagreed and Agreed. respondents agreed that they know of LLITNs is better than ITNs. 7%) Disagreed and 199(33.2%) were Undecided. The percentage rating that Disagreed is ranked highest, followed by Undecided and Agreed.

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Table 2: Effective usage of ITNS

Insecticide treatment nets been	s N	usage of INS	Agreed	Disagreed	Undecided	Total	l0
0		There is not enough room and space to tie or fix the ITNs	439 (73%) (60.7%)	120 (20%) (15.3%)	41 (7%) (24%)	600 (100%) (100%)	have used
		against mosquito bites and have given substantial protection against malaria.	(59%)	(40.7%)	(16.7%)	(100%)	
12		home environment does not support using of ITNs consistently during bedtime.	346 (75.67%)	244 (24.3%)	10	600 (100%)	
13		Usage of ITNS is expensive because it does not last long	454	146	-	600	
		ITNs causes Discomfort (heat sweat/difficulty breathing)	(3406) 204	(66%) 396	-	(100%) 600	
		ITNs IS misuse (hung over windows, used as	(65) 392	(21.3%) 128	(13.3%) 80	(100%) 600	
			364	600			

Individuals
blanket)

Table 2 above revealed that 439(73%) agreed that there is not enough room and space to tie or fix the ITNs, 120(20%) disagreed and 41(7%) were undecided, 364(60.7%) respondents agreed that Insecticide treatment nets have been used against mosquito bites and have given substantial protection against malaria, 92(15.3%) disagreed and 144(24%) were undecided. 346(59%) respondents agreed that their home environment does not support using of ITNs consistently during bedtime. Also, 244(40.7%) disagreed and 10(1.67%) were undecided. 454(75.7%) respondents agreed that usage of ITNs is expensive because it does not last long, 146(24.3%) disagreed. 204(34%) respondents agreed that ITNs causes discomfort (heat/sweat/difficulty in breathing): and 396(66%) disagreed. 392(65.3%) respondents agreed that ITNs is misuse (hung over windows, used as blanket) by individuals, 128(21.3%) disagreed and 13.3%) were undecided.

Table 3: Challenges facing ITNS/LLIN

Challenges facing ITNS/LLIN		Agreed	Disagreed	Undecided	Total
	I can't use ITNs effectively, daily and consistently for sleeping due to overcrowding	429 (71.5%)	171 (28.5%)		600 (100%)
17	Lack of consistent power supply to prevent heat discourages usage of ITNs consistently	463 (77%)	56 (2%)	123 (21%)	600 (100%)
18	Lack of affordability to replace ITNs/LLIN immediately is a challenge.	479 (79.8%)	56 (2%)	123 (21%)	600 (100%)

Table 3 revealed that respondents agreed that they can't use ITNS effectively and consistently for sleeping and 171 (28.5%), disagreed. The percentage rating shows that Agreed ranked highest, followed by disagreed. 463(77%) agreed that Lack of consistent power supply to prevent heat discourages their usage Of I consistently, disagreed and 123(21%) were undecided. The percentage ratings that agreed is ranked highest, followed by undecided total and disagreed

Table 4: LLIN/ITNs usage and drops in malaria

SN	LLIN/ITNs usage and drops in malaria	Agreed	Disagreed	Undecided	Total
19	LLIN usage has helped drops in malaria morbidity	559 (93%)	21 (4%)	20 (3%)	600 (100%)
20	ITNs usage has reduced drops in malaria deaths among inhabitants of Warri	463 (77%)	14 (2%)	123 (21%)	600 (100%)

ITNs malaria usage occurrence has reduced of Warri and consistent treatment among inhabitants of Warri, 56(9%) disagreed and 65(11%) were undecided.

Table 4 revealed that 559(93%) respondents agreed that LLIN usage has helped drops in malaria morbidity, 21 (4%) disagreed and 20(3%) were undecided. This shows that a high percentage of the respondents know the advantages of long lasting insecticide treated nets. However, 463(77%) of Warri inhabitants agreed that has reduced deaths amongst them, 14(2%) disagreed and 123 (21%) were undecided. 479(80%) respondents agreed that ITNS usage has reduced consistent malaria occurrence and treatment among inhabitants of Warri, 56(9%) disagreed and 65(11%) were undecided.

Discussion of Findings

Table one revealed that despite the facts that most of the respondents agreed that ITNs are efficient in protection against mosquitoes bite, a high percentage of the respondent prefers insecticide spray and window nets to ITNs. This study confirms why a high percentage of the respondents stated that their home environment does not support the use of ITNs. The study also revealed that ITNs gets dilly easily because of our dusty tropical (weather) environment.

66% of the respondent opined that ITNs causes discomfort while 34% disagreed. This could be possible since a high percentage of the respondents have Problem of space to hang and fix the ITNs. This is possible because of challenges Of accommodation and overcrowding of people in some neighbourhood in Warri metropolis. There is indications that some of the respondents prefers other method Of preventing mosquitoes bite since they will not be subjected to heat rash and the need to wash and change their ITNs as the need arise. The various challenges among Warri inhabitants in the use of ITNs to prevent malaria parasites are poor

accommodation; poor cross ventilation, overcrowding, lack of consistent power supply to prevent heat during high humidity period, inadequate funds to replace Nets/LLINs immediately if torn, because ITNs is very expensive for an average Nigerian and inadequate space to hang the ITNs.

However, a high percentage of the respondents confirmed the fact that ITNs is highly effective in the prevention of mosquitoes bite. of the

also revealed that they lack knowledge in fixing the ITNs thereby its
71.50% of the respondents revealed that they don't use ITNs

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daily and consistently. This will definitely increase the rate of mosquitoes bite and thereby increase the rate at which most Warri inhabitants will be exposed to malaria parasites.

Conclusion

Conclusively, a high percentage of Warri metropolis have the awareness of insecticide treated nets and long lasting insecticide treated but quite a highly percentages revealed that the environment does not support the consistent usage of ITNs. Therefore, there is need for advocacy through constant health education programmes to encourage the use of ITNs in Warri metropolis noting the fact that Warri environment is a riverine area that encourages the breed of mosquitoes. Based on the findings, the researcher made the following recommendations:

1. There is need for health educators and allied health professionals to conduct research to understand why the usage of ITNs is very low in Warri metropolis.
2. Health care providers and health educators need to organise health educative programmes to encourage the usage of ITNs/LUTNs among Warri metropolis.
3. There is need for government to collaborate with health care provider to strategize and proffer solutions to the challenges confronting the usage of ITNs in Warri metropolis
4. Individuals and Warri inhabitants should be encouraged to understand that preventive medicine is cheaper than curative medicine of consistent treatment of malaria fever
3. Health educators should practically advocate their peers and friends on the advantage of using ITNs.

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